

Predicting burnout among non-profit organization (NPO) workers: the roles of psychological capital and emotional labour

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ABSTRACT: Non-profit organisations (NPOs) play a significant role in the development of healthy communities by providing essential services that help to maintain economic stability and mobility. They also help to improve communities in many ways. These organisations, on the other hand, will not be able to survive and function effectively if their employees suffer from burnout that hinders their performance and affects the team's effectiveness which is essential for a non-profit organisation to achieve its goals. Therefore, this quantitative cross-sectional study aims to examine the link between psychological capital (PsyCap) and burnout, as well as the link between emotional labour and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers. An online questionnaire survey was carried out to 164 respondents from a non-profit organisation, including its employees from local and international branches. The study is among the few Malaysian data to empirically investigate the effects of four dimensions of PsyCap i.e., Self-Efficacy, Optimism, Hope, and Resilience as well as two dimensions of emotional labour i.e., Surface Acting, and Deep Acting towards burnout. This study complements the burnout literature on NPO workers as a limited applicable study on the subject would be a solid base to initiate other researches around the world, especially in Malaysia. The findings of this study could give an insight into the role of PsyCap within the Malaysian context, a further understanding of the prevalence of Malaysia's workers' burnout, and insight into the severe importance of emotional labour in improving NPO workers.

Keywords: Psychological Capital, Emotional Labour, Burnout, Non-Profit Organization (NPO), Hope, Efficacy, Resilience, Optimism, Surface Acting, Deep Acting

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1. Introduction

Burnout was among the epidemics that had been categorised as potentially "contagious" and perpetuated itself through informal interactions on the job. Recently the World Health Organization (WHO) has included burnout in the 11th Revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) as an occupational phenomenon. Hence, workers' burnout is a cause for concern because it has detrimental implications for the affected person, the broader organisation, and the customers or community they serve. The burnout syndrome shows itself with exhaustion as physical fatigue and emotional depletion. With the current state of shortages of staff and work overloads, Malaysian non-profit organizations (NPO) are concerned about the backlash concerning the services rendered to the public. Steps need to be taken early to determine the current well-being situation among NPO staff as Malaysia is assertively moving towards becoming one of the aged countries by 2030. The physical signs of burnout are headaches, stomach pain, nausea, tightness of muscles, and chronic recurring fatigue. Burnout symptoms are stressors in mental health, such as anxiety, depression, and sleep problems. Individuals with burnout seem to withdraw emotionally and physiologically from their jobs, expend less time and energy in living, do only certain activities, and often miss work. High-quality work takes time energy, dedication, and imagination, but a burned-out person would not be accessible by themselves.

The bottom line of burnout is the decline in the quality and quantity of work produced (Schaufeli, 2017; Keri et al., 2020; Rafael et al., 2021). NPO workers help people develop, handle, and solve problems to address personal, family, and work difficulties (FSU Online, 2020). Miller (2022) examined the increased sensitivity of NPO workers to stress because of their attention to the needs of others. The high workload was related to impaired health and well-being (Chron, 2021). The workload is seen as physically and psychologically tiring. The effect is abuse and un acknowledgement (Gozzoli et al., 2018). As the world's population is ageing rapidly by 2050, around 16% of the world's population will be elderly, according to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2019). Most developed countries have accepted the average age of 65 as a definition of elderly (Bilgili & Kitiş, 2017). The proportion of the world's population over 60 years is also projected to increase from 12 per cent to 22 per cent between 2015 and 2050 (WHO, 2019). While existence is extended for chronic diseases, the need for and care for the elderly is growing as the current pandemic Covid-19 is particularly dangerous for the elderly. Akgun-Citak et al. (2019) have found that in four countries, it is expected that there are difficulties in handling human services caregiver's own life and coping with emotions. The challenges of being a carer or caregiver must be explored.

Therefore, a thorough grasp of social workers' burnout, its dynamics, and how to overcome it is crucial to remain committed to a great cause and maintain compassion and commitment. After nearly 50 years, burnout is now a trend that seems true to people's shared experiences. It inspired researchers to study and understand what it is and why. It has encouraged clinicians to find ways of dealing with, avoiding, or fighting it. Burnout has thus been recognised as a social problem worthy of attention by both researchers and professionals. Since this recognition has spread to many other nations, it has become a phenomenon of extraordinary international significance. Instead of viewing burnout as a

state, research is moving to look at burnout as a process (Maslach, 2017). This approach proves advantageous, as it empowers individuals to intervene promptly upon detecting signs of pressure or anxiety, eliminating the need to wait for NPO workers to reach a breaking point. NPO workers and their departments will take responsibility for managing this phenomenon to excel in the social care field (FSU Online, 2020). Currently, the World Health Organization (WHO) is embarking on developing evidence-based guidelines on mental wellbeing in the workplace, and about time Malaysia acts toward the same.

Problem Statement

Burnout in the context of Malaysian NPO Workers is relatively new to the research world, which presents a challenge for researchers who are attempting to further fine-tune the existing body of knowledge within the context of Malaysia. According to Maslach and Leiter (2016), reliable data are scarce regarding the factors that protect against burnout and those that put people at risk of experiencing it across various demographics, personality traits, and types. There is a lack of consensus and confusion regarding almost every demographic factor that has been investigated, with contradictory findings regarding the effects of gender, age, ethnicity, marital status, and parental status on burnout. The percentage of human service workers who report feeling burned out on their jobs has been steadily climbing. According to the Child Welfare Workforce 2004 report published by the American Public Human Services Association (APHSA) in 2005, factors that contribute to worker turnover include heavy workloads, heavy caseloads, after-hours work, amount and type of paperwork, insufficient resources, lack of career advancement, and low salaries. These factors can also be contributing factors to STS symptoms. Burnout among workers would lead to a decrease in overall employee performance and motivation, according to research conducted by Pan (2017), Margaretha (2019), and Stefan (2020).

Psychological Capital and Emotional Labour are two factors that can significantly contribute to burnout among workers. Psychological capital refers to an individual's positive psychological resources, including self-efficacy (belief in one's ability to accomplish tasks), optimism (positive outlook on future outcomes), hope (perseverance and goal-directedness), and resilience (ability to bounce back from challenges). While these qualities are generally beneficial, they can also have negative implications if not managed properly, leading to burnout. Individuals with high psychological capital may set ambitious goals for themselves, believing they can overcome any obstacle. However, consistently striving for perfection and pushing oneself too hard can result in chronic stress and exhaustion, contributing to burnout. Emotional labour involves the regulation of emotions to meet job requirements, often requiring employees to display specific emotions regardless of their true feelings. This is particularly relevant in jobs that involve direct interactions with clients, customers, or service users. While emotional labour is necessary, it can lead to burnout under certain circumstances. When employees are required to express emotions that conflict with their genuine feelings, it creates emotional dissonance. Continuously suppressing or faking emotions can be emotionally draining and contribute to burnout over time.

In summary, both psychological capital and emotional labour can contribute to burnout when individuals struggle to manage the demands they bring. High psychological capital can lead to overexertion and unrealistic expectations, while emotional labour can lead to emotional exhaustion and inauthenticity. To prevent burnout, individuals and organizations need to foster a balanced approach to goal setting, stress management, emotional regulation, and self-care. While there has been a growing interest in understanding the factors contributing to burnout among NPO workers, a significant research gap exists in exploring the relationships between psychological capital, emotional labour, and burnout. The Malaysian context, with its unique cultural, religious, and social dynamics, provides an intriguing backdrop for investigating these relationships, which could shed light on how these factors interplay and influence burnout among NPO workers in Malaysia. This context-specific exploration can provide a nuanced understanding of these relationships, with findings that may apply to other regions with similar cultural dynamics. By addressing this research gap, the study has the potential to contribute not only to academic literature but also to practical implications for human resource management and organizational development in the context of welfare organizations in Malaysia.

2. Literature Review

Burnout

The word "burnout" refers to a phenomenon related to the treatment and services of people dealing with people who are emotionally taxing (Maslach et al., 2001). Burnout was first described as "a state of tiredness or frustration caused by dedication to a cause, way of life or connection ship that could not deliver the expected benefit" (Freudenberger & Richelson, 1981) and later described as "a psychological syndrome in the face of chronic interpersonal stressors on the job" by Maslach et al. (2001). It was first used to describe someone who could not do their job. Burnout was defined by Devilly et al. (2009) as a mental state characterized by persistent work stress. Burnout is described by three factors: a) emotional and physical fatigue, b) withdrawal from work (including cynicism manifested in adverse job reactions), and c) a sense of ineffectiveness manifests itself in a belief that you have achieved nothing (Portero de la Cruz et al., 2020; Bang & Reio, 2017). Burnout is generated by work-related events, not exposing clients to stressful situations (Sergio et al., 2022). Burnout is most often caused by high case numbers and increased paperwork, inadequate support, staff shortages due to a lack of new hires, and overwork (Poon et al., 2022; Talaee, et al., 2022). Burnout affects social workers, teachers, and police officers (Maslach, 2003) as well as nurses, doctors, psychotherapists, counsellors, psychiatrists, pastors, and childcare workers. Burnout has also been reported in long-term care workers (Kimes, 2016) and nurses (Shah et al., 2021). Sexual abuse therapists working with sex offenders also suffer from burnout (Baum & Moyal, 2018).

According to Freudenberger and Richelson (1981), feelings of alienation, poor cognitive functions, despair, fear, heart failure, insomnia, loss of idealism, and loss of spirit are all symptoms of burnout. Maslach et al. (2001) describe burnout in addition to emotional depletion, depersonalization, and the feeling of professional achievement as emotional depletion, the loss of self-esteem, and the accomplishment of professional performance.

When stress and role conflicts meet high expectations and a lack of self-care, emotional depletion develops. People can become depersonalized due to increased work-related stress, ongoing personal engagement, work pressures, and dealing with customer complaints and challenges. To measure when a person's professional success is waning, you can look for signs of lack of recognition, feelings of inadequacy, ineffective leadership, lack of participation in decision-making, and lack of respect without a reward system (Tutar et al., 2020). Burnout is a work-related illness with several adverse effects on businesses, including absenteeism, high turnover, and a breakdown in care continuity. Burnout hurts employees' mental and physical health. Employees are subjected to negative repercussions such as substance abuse and marriage problems (Wilkerson et al., 2017). Individuals categorized as burnout can impact work relationships through personalized conflict and workflow disruption (Maslach, 2016). The Maslach burnout inventory (MBI) developed by Maslach and Jackson (1981) is one of the most widely used and considered the "standard tool for research in this field and has been translated and validated in many languages" (Maslach & Leiter, 2016, p. 104).

Burnout has been associated with several forms of adverse effects on the physical and mental health of the worker (Abramson, 2022; Baka, 2015; Maslach & Leiter, 2016; Ozturk & Ay, 2018). The fatigue factor of burnout is the most predictive of stress-based health and behavioural outcomes than the other two components (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Work burnout can also lead to death, which is considered the ultimate result of work burnout (Kalra & Sahay, 2018). The research on factors associated with burnout syndrome is exceptionally inconsistent. An extensive study on age and burnout syndrome has yielded mixed results (Amofo et al., 2015; Arrogante & Aparicio-Zaldivar, 2017; De la Fuente-Solana et al., 2017; Gmez-Urquiza et al., 2017). According to certain academicians, burnout syndrome can arise due to a deficiency of experience within a particular domain (Iorga et al., 2017; Kutluturkan et al., 2016; McKinley et al., 2017). Burnout syndrome is associated with a rise in tension, dread, and despair (Lebares et al., 2018; Pereira-Lima & Loureiro, 2015; Upadyaya et al., 2016). NPO worker burnout is a state of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged stress and pressure. In Malaysia, NPO workers may experience burnout due to a number of factors, such as high caseloads, lack of support and resources, and the emotional toll of working with vulnerable populations (Pang et al., 2022). As a result of the lack of consistency in data on components associated with burnout syndrome, forecasting the condition might be challenging (Shahid & Muchiri, 2019).

Psychological Capital

The term "psychological capital" refers to "an individual's positive psychological state of development," which is characterised as "hope, resiliency, strong self-efficacy, and optimism" (Luthans et al., 2015, p.3). The next section will go into more detail about each of these characters. Individuals with high psychological capital, according to Luthans et al. (2015, p.3), had the confidence of self-efficacy to sustain their effort until they succeeded when faced with challenges; were optimistic about succeeding; persevered in pursuing their goals while remaining hopeful in their pursuit of success; were resilient when faced with problems and adversity until they succeeded. Bandura (1999) stated that leaders needed

four critical resources to build efficacy, which was related to psychological capital. Psychological capital is based on job motivation literature (Stajkovic, 2006), positive psychology literature (Lopes & Synder, 2009), and social cognition literature (Lynn et al., 2022). Psychological Capital (PsyCap) was developed as a mechanism that can lead to positive well-being because of its defensive existence (Wang et al., 2022). The optimistic psychological approach to the well-being of workers has given rise to a stronger emphasis on positive organizational behaviour (POB) (Manuti & Giancaspro, 2018). Psychological capital is one of the buildings that display promise in identifying variables that encourage employees' health.

Research has shown that, on the other hand, these traits can be dispositional, part of the personality and culture, which vary in circumstances such as Yin et al. (2016), accept that psychological capital has a beneficial impact on the mental regulatory mechanism and decreases employees' emotional fatigue. Individuals with high PsyCap scores, according to Newman et al. (2014), have more optimistic views for the future and better confidence in their capacity to deal with obstacles at work than those with lower scores. Individuals who experience these favourable psychological states are more likely to put forth the effort and perform well, which in turn increases job satisfaction (Newman et al., 2014). PsyCap is a critical construct since it is state-like and influences intended attitudinal, behavioural, and performance outcomes (Da et al., 2021). Psychological capital consists of four distinct characteristics: hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism. Together, these four qualities prepare the individual to trust in challenging duties, to believe in their abilities to excel and to conquer adversity.

Hope

Characteristics like optimism and hope have been associated with both physical and mental health (Du et al., 2015). "Hopeful thought reflects the conviction that one may identify pathways to desired goals and become motivated to use those pathways," claim Snyder et al. (2003). Thus, hope is a mental process that encourages the development of willpower (a goal-directed determination) and willpower (planning strategies to achieve goals), both of which result in good emotions (the expectation of meeting desired goals). Hope is frequently seen as a mindset or style of thinking that is based on the conviction that change is possible as well as the anticipation that the future will be positive. Higher self-esteem and lower levels of self-deprecating thoughts are typically reported by people who express higher levels of hope. Hope is considered to be closely related to "agency," or the degree to which a person feels they have control over their lives, concerning resolving mental health issues or inappropriate medication use (also referred to as "Recovery"). The idea that hopes and self-belief can be boosted by exposure to people who have been in a similar circumstance and have subsequently found a means to overcome their problems is central to the mechanism viewed as most powerful in raising hope within the "Recovery Movements." This process is known as "Visible Recovery." Increasing optimism can enhance opinions of one's efficacy.

Efficacy

Self-efficacy is considered the foundation of human organizations (Bandura et al., 1999). As a person's confidence in their capacity to mobilize the motivation, cognitive capital, and organization to tackle a situation, Bandura has conceptualized self-efficacy. It is the conviction that one has the potential to accomplish a certain outcome or aim (Bandura et al., 1999). There is also perseverance among those who believe in their abilities to control their feelings in the face of adverse circumstances. These individuals are often more likely to ignore pessimistic feelings about themselves and their potential than people with a sense of ineffectiveness (Scott, 2022). Bandura et al. (1999) believed that challenging work tasks could be deferred by individuals reserving their credentials. When these individuals have a challenging mission, we are presumed to dwell on bad consequences and thus have a higher degree of fear, dwelling on their future shortcomings rather than on how to solve the dilemma. It is then said that certain people contribute their failure to personal deficits. Individuals with self-efficacy, on the other hand, have greater faith in their skills and therefore expend more time searching for a solution. In their efforts, we are more diligent and, thus, more effective in challenging and usually difficult activities. Self-efficacy is equated to resilience through the idea that self-efficacy contributes significantly to an individual's ability to adapt and cope with challenging circumstances (Sabouripour et al., 2021). When individuals have a strong sense of self-efficacy, they are more likely to believe that their actions and efforts can lead to successful outcomes. This belief fuels their motivation to tackle challenges head-on and employ effective problem-solving strategies. Such proactive and adaptive coping mechanisms are key aspects of resilience. A significant volume of studies has shown self-efficacy as a vital element.

Resilience

The definition of resilience has developed over the last four decades as it appears in the scientific literature (Cicchetti, 2010). As a result, there was a lack of consensus on the definition (Bonanno & Keltner, 2004; Luthar et al., 2000; Masten, 2007; Olsson et al., 2003). Nevertheless, three general concept definitions have been defined in the comprehensive resilience literature as a whole: resilience as a result, as a mechanism, and as a characteristic of personality (Ya et al., 2014). Despite threats, resilience, as a consequence, has been described as an effective adaptation to acute stresses and persistent adversity (Mahdiani & Ungar, 2021; Chmitorz et al., 2018). Resilience has been defined as a complex mechanism for adjusting to a risk scenario involving the relationship between risk factors and protective resources within the framework of the process. Resilience can be defined as a positive personality characteristic in the general personality trait category that helps people to recover from adversity and to adapt, prosper and improve in the face of adverse circumstances. While these three categories of concern narrowly specified resilience, resilience will be viewed as a personality attribute for this analysis, which helps the participant recover from hardship and prosper. Resilience, thus created, makes it clearer to compare with other personality qualities. Resilient employees are better able to bounce back from setbacks or hurdles and return to or exceed their prior level of productivity (Craig & Muskat, 2013).

Optimism

Making a confident assumption about achieving success both now and in the future is the definition of optimism. Positive events are more likely to be internalized and credited by those who have a low external locus of control. They think they must put forth effort for nice things to occur. However, optimists think that wonderful things will always come to them in the future. The key to increasing optimism is shifting your attention. It can be developed by exercises in accepting the past, savouring the present, and seeing opportunities in the future. How we evaluate the past affects how well we can anticipate the future. An individual's general conviction that they will encounter more favourable circumstances than unfavourable ones in the future is referred to as optimism. It also looks at how people interpret the factors that led to both positive and negative past occurrences to form expectations for the future. According to this viewpoint, pessimists ascribe causes of poor experiences to internal forces, such as believing that things going wrong are their responsibility, whereas optimists attribute causes of negative experiences to external forces, such as bad luck. Conversely, pessimistic people attribute achievement to chance, whilst optimistic people attribute it to their ability (Çavuş & Gökçen, 2015).

The Relationship between Psychological Capital and Burnout

Psychological capital is one of the buildings that display promise in identifying variables that encourage the health of employees. As mentioned before, PsyCap consists of four distinct characteristics: hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism. Together, these four qualities prepare the individual to trust in challenging duties, to believe in their abilities to excel and to conquer adversity. Previous conducted research has examined the relationship between resilience and burnout syndrome. The resilience of the PsyCap construct has been associated with the avoidance and relief of symptoms associated with burnout syndrome (Arrogante & Aparicio-Zaldivar, 2017; Rosenberg, 2018; Rushton et al., 2015). Rushton et al. (2015) conducted a quantitative correlation study to determine the components of a healthy work environment that included examining the relationship between resilience, hope, and burnout syndrome among nurses. The findings indicated a relatively strong negative correlation between the emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and resilience components of burnout syndrome in the nursing staff surveyed (Rushton et al., 2015). The burnout syndrome's component of personal performance was revealed to be positively associated with resilience. Additionally, the study showed statistically significant relationships between hope and burnout syndrome. Rushton et al. (2015) established a relationship between hope and nursing burnout. Hope, in particular, was found to have a substantial negative correlation with emotional fatigue (-0.34) and depersonalization symptoms of burnout syndrome (-0.31) (Rushton et al., 2015).

On the other side, hope was positively correlated with the individual performance component of burnout syndrome (0.43) (Rushton et al., 2015). These data indicate that as individuals' hope develops, their perceptions of their accomplishments and effectiveness improve, while their emotional tiredness, depersonalization, and cynicism decrease. The literature has also examined the relationship between self-efficacy and burnout syndrome.

Self-efficacy is negatively correlated with burnout syndrome (Amiri et al., 2019; Onuoha & Idemudia, 2017). While optimism has been associated with increased levels of work and organisational engagement, it has also been associated with decreased levels of physical and mental health (Fortes et al., 2020). The present study explores the effects of the four constituents of PsyCap, namely self-efficacy, hope, resilience, and optimism on burnout. While previous research has linked burnout to psychological problems and stress, none have specifically examined the dimensions of PsyCap. Therefore, this study aims to bridge that knowledge gap with its findings. Therefore, the hypotheses for these relationships are as follows:

- I. Hypothesis 1 (H1): There is a significant relationship between the psychological capital's dimension of hope and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers.
- II. Hypothesis 2 (H2): There is a significant relationship between the psychological capital's dimension of efficacy and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers.
- III. Hypothesis 3 (H3): There is a significant relationship between the psychological capital's dimension of resilience and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers.
- IV. Hypothesis 4 (H4): There is a significant relationship between the psychological capital's dimension of optimism and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers.

Emotional Labour

Emotion refers to a complex psychological and physiological state that involves a range of subjective feelings, physiological changes, expressive behaviours, and cognitive processes. It arises in response to various stimuli, both external and internal, and plays a crucial role in shaping an individual's thoughts, actions, and interactions with the environment. Emotions encompass a wide spectrum of experiences, such as happiness, sadness, anger, fear, surprise, and disgust, among others (Levenson, 2019). Emotional contagion is the term used to describe the various moods and feelings that a worker in an organisation may pick up from a co-worker or associate. In essence, this concept demonstrates that human feelings are contagious and occasionally pass from one person to another. Doherty (1997) identified five fundamental emotions: happiness, love, anger, fear, and sadness. Emotional Labour refers to the action of the management of emotions and emotional expressions to align with organizational rules defined as emotions necessary in organizational terms in emotional expressions with organizational rules defined as emotions that are organizationally necessary for the process of interpersonal relationships to correspond to relationships (Hochschild, 2003; Mikolajczak et al., 2007). Another definition of emotional labour is the effort to understand others, show empathy towards others, and feel the emotions of others as if they were their own emotions (Basm & Beenirba, 2012). Emotional labour is now an essential part of various professions and service fields (Adams & Mastracci, 2018; Yucebalkan & Karasakal, 2016). These professions include, in particular, doctors, nurses, teachers, airline staff, social workers, call centre employees, and sales representatives (Han et al., 2022; Bayram et al., 2012). Emotional labour pertains to displaying appropriate emotions to enhance job performance (Kumar et al., 2022).

The process of managing one's feelings after wages was described by Hochschild (2003) as emotional work. This process involves eliminating, altering, faking, or changing

emotions to comply with the organization's presentation laws and its role as a job (Jeung et al., 2018; Lee & Ok, 2012; Hochschild, 2003). Two emotional management processes are used in the intensive study: (a) surface acting or regulating imagined feelings on the surface; and (b) deep acting or moving thoughts (Grandey, 2000; Hochschild, 2003). Feelings are manipulated or falsified to change the emotional expression to align with the rules of organizational or work performance (Grandey & Gabriel, 2015; Lisa et al., 2019; Ivona & Gerben, 2017). Emotional work is a process in which individuals can manage emotions through surface activity, which is a dynamic and meaningful process by manipulating their feelings to demonstrate the emotion required (Grandey, 2000; Hochschild, 2003). Surface acting is linked to a diminished sense of personal success, hypothesized by Hochschild (2003) for shame and frustration. However, research reveals that when deep acting adjusts internal thoughts and feelings to suit the display laws, it minimizes differences and is not about fatigue. Internal harmonization of emotions with corporate guidelines helps increase professional accomplishment and lower detachment levels (Brotheridge & Grandey, 2002). From the viewpoint of organizations, mental well-being is correlated with improved efficiency, fewer turnovers, and absenteeism (Scanlan & Still, 2019; Bowers et al., 2021; Yasir et al., 2020). From a worker's viewpoint, emotional well-being improves physical and mental health, engagement, and happiness with the job (Kun & Gadanez, 2022; Ruggeri et al., 2020).

Two principal methods exist for employees to enact emotional labour: surface acting (SA) and deep acting (DA). Surface acting involves feigning the display of a specific emotion without a corresponding internal sentiment, whereas deep acting entails a genuine attempt to cultivate the requisite emotion before its external manifestation. Surface acting can sometimes be perceived as insincere, as it necessitates assuming a demeanour that is devoid of authenticity, while deep acting is generally regarded as authentic and heartfelt. Deep acting represents a form of emotion regulation focused on pre-emptively addressing emotional circumstances, whereas surface acting constitutes a form of emotion regulation directed at swiftly responding to impromptu demands for emotional expressions (Byrne et al., 2011). Meanwhile, individual emotional work should be analysed as distinct types of emotion regulation that employ strenuous emotional work strategies such as surface acting and deep acting to regulate feelings and emotional expressions (Grandey, 2000). Surface action entails faking emotions not felt or concealing feelings. In contrast, deep action entails modifying or transforming the emotions felt into more desirable ones through reassessment or attention (Hochschild, 2003). Grandey (2000) defines emotional work as an emotion regulation process in which both superficial (i.e., changing expressions) and deep (i.e., changing feelings) actions can be used. Service employees may acquire willpower and energy to invest in deep acting during service encounters (Chen & Fellenz, 2020).

The individual's emotional regulation is at the heart of emotional work (Grandey & Melloy, 2017). It is critical to understand the exchange value of emotional labour and the exhibition rules or work requirements of various professions. As a result of the emotional wear and tear, they may develop negative and cynical attitudes toward others, as well as dehumanising and indifferent reactions, which can lead to low productivity and, ultimately, poor evaluation (Edú-Valsania et al., 2022). It is imperative for employees to proficiently manage their emotions to ensure that these interactions remain affable and enduring. This

often entails adhering to the prescribed facial expressions and behavioural norms stipulated by the organization as part of their job obligations. However, this emotional exertion can frequently culminate in recurring emotional fatigue, job discontentment, and elevated turnover rates, all of which carry substantial implications for service enterprises (Grandey, 2000). NPO workers in Malaysia often engage in emotional labour as part of their daily work, as they interact with clients who may be dealing with difficult personal and social issues. This can include managing their own emotions to maintain a professional demeanour, as well as regulating the emotions of clients to help them cope with their situations. Emotional labour can be draining for social workers and can contribute to burnout if not managed properly.

The Relationship between Emotional Labour and Burnout

While there is increasing evidence of stress, emotional work, and burnout symptoms, the various factors of emotional work as a prognosis for burnout have not been adequately considered in research. It was widely assumed that "caregiving" professions are something special that makes their jobs feel more fulfilling. The literature demonstrates that when dealing with difficult situations, conflict and commitment to emotional management lead to stress and emotions connected with burnout (Brotheridge & Grandey, 2002). Interactions with frequent and long-term customers were viewed as a precedent to burnout (Blomstrom-Johnson, 2021). Jobs that require significant emotional labour, especially if the emotions expressed are not genuine, can contribute to emotional exhaustion and lead to burnout (Zhang et al., 2021; Kaur & Malodia, 2013). Emotional work strategies, especially superficial actions, have often been associated with poor employee well-being (Sciotto & Pace, 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). Grandey's (2000) framework aids in the comprehension of emotional work and its related constructs. First, the initiation of emotional work is closely related to situational cues, such as general interaction expectations and real-time emotional events. Second, strenuous emotional work can have long-term consequences, both in terms of individual (e.g., burnout or job satisfaction) and organisational (e.g., performance or work avoidance behaviour) well-being. According to the findings of a recent literature review by Jeung et al. (2018), emotional labour is a current job stressor in modern society that leads to burnout, and research into personality traits such as self-efficacy is critical to understanding the relationship between emotional labour and its consequences, such as burnout.

Depending on the job, burnout appears to be much more common in customer service personnel rather than in manufacturing industries (Morgan, 2022). With a high emotional workload, these findings suggest that caregiver burnout should be given more attention (Gérain & Zech, 2019). Several meta-analyses have shown, for example, that surface actions (Hori & Chao, 2019; Meinert, 2017; Kammeyer-Mueller et al., 2013; Thomas et al., 2017) and negative presentation rules are positively associated with employee burnout (Salama et al., 2022; Dudley, 2017). Nevertheless, an opposing picture of emotional work has emerged that highlights unfavourable results linked with emotional labour could be a result of poor person-job fit rather than the usage of such tactics per se (Humphrey et al., 2015). It takes effort and a deep part of an employee's individuality to

show the appropriate emotion in each situation. When a business regulates an employee's emotions, it can harm their physical and mental well-being, as well as lead to burnout (Hochschild, 2003). Therefore, the hypotheses for these relationships are as follows:

- I. Hypothesis 5 (H5): There is a significant relationship between emotional labour's dimension of surface acting and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers.
- II. Hypothesis 6 (H6): There is a significant relationship between emotional labour's dimension of deep acting and burnout among Malaysian NPO workers.

Figure 1. Research framework

3. Methodology

The cross-sectional quantitative study was conducted as this design of study provides insight into a complicated topic through scientific and focused study and focuses on the aims and relationships researched (Sang, 2008). As per Figure 1, the independent variables in this study were PsyCap and emotional labour. Meanwhile, in this study, the dependent variable was burnout. Type of investigation is correlational study to describe the variables in research framework to identify the relationships between the variables. Extent of researcher interference is a minimal and the study setting is non-contrived. The study surveyed all 164 employees of a Malaysian NPO from its headquarters located in Shah Alam, Selangor, and all branches in Perak, Pahang, Borneo of Malaysia, and from Indonesia, Egypt, Africa, Japan, and New Zealand as well. Thus, the respondents must be from personnel who have worked for the organisation for at least three months who have committed as a project unit, and work full-time, contract, and part-time. They are scattered across different divisions, including operations, marketing, creative, public relation, finance, human resource, and others. For this research, the researcher did not make sampling

technique because of limitation of data and choose to use census technique. An online questionnaire through e-survey has been distributed to 164 employees who were all elements of the population to collect data in this study.

All data was collected via the online survey questionnaire. Respondents are indirectly involved in the management and operation of the NPO's headquarter and all branches in Malaysia and overseas. The respondents were given two weeks of working days to complete the questionnaires. In return, the researcher received 122 sets of questionnaires, however upon closer inspection, only 118 sets are deemed eligible as the other 4 sets have either incomplete data or inconsistent data and have to be rejected during the data entry phase. The Social Science Statistics Package (SPSS) version 26 was used to analyse the data. The data analysis process begins with determining the demographic features of the data using descriptive statistics such as percentage, mean, frequency, and standard deviation. The following analyses were normality test to determine the data's normality by examining the distribution's shape and internal consistency using the reliability analysis. In this study, multiple regression analysis investigated the predictive values of PsyCap and emotional labour on burnout. Multiple regression can be considered a "sophisticated extension of correlation" (Pallant, 2010). It is used to determine the predictive potential of a group of independent variables concerning a continuous dependent variable. It discussed the linear relationship between two or more variables by analysing the data collected from respondents using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Data has been collected using four pre-existing instruments: Psychological Capital Questionnaires (PSQ), Emotional Labour Scale (ELS), and Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI) Questionnaires. Psychological Capital (PsyCap) was measured using the Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ-24). The Psychological Capital scale is the most commonly used measure to assess PsyCap (Luthans et al., 2015). The PCQ is 24 items that comprise six items per each of the four PsyCap subscales of efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience (Luthans et al., 2015). Participants would be asked to think about themselves and rate their level of agreement with each of the items on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). In a validity analysis, Luthans et al. (2015) found internal consistency reliability of .89 for the PCQ. Emotional labour was measured using Brotheridge and Lee's (2003) fifteen-item self-report questionnaire based on a theoretical model proposed by Hochschild (2003). The scale is composed of 15 items, one item referring to the duration of the interaction (A typical interaction with customers lasts about ___ minutes) and 14 items distributed into five subscales: (a) Frequency (I display specific emotions required by my job); (b) Intensity (I display intense emotions at work); (c) Variety (I display many different kinds of emotions at work); (d) Superficial representation (I resist expressing my true feelings at work); and (e) Deep representation (I really try to experience the emotions I should display at work). The items are assessed through a 5-point Likert scale ranging from never (1) to always (5). The original scale presents satisfactory Cronbach's alpha values varying from .74 to .91.

Burnout was measured using the renowned Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI) by Kristensen et al., (2005). CBI is a 16-item inventory that focuses on 3 main areas of burnout: personally related burnout (six items; e.g., "How often do you think: "I can't take it anymore?", "How often do you feel weak and susceptible to illness?"); work-related burnout

(seven items; e.g., “Are you exhausted in the morning at the thought of another day at work?”; “Do you feel worn out at the end of the working day?”) and client /customer related burnout (six items; e.g., “Does it drain your energy to work with clients?”; “Do you feel that you give more than you get back when you work with clients?”). Items were rated using a 5-Point Likert Scale (1 “Never/almost never or To a very low degree”, 2 “Seldom or To a low degree”, 3 “Sometimes or Somewhat”, 4 “Often or To a high degree” and 5 “Always or To a very high degree”. The Cronbach’s alpha for internal reliability is very high (.85 - .87). While the MBI has remained popular in social science research, the CBI has become the measure of choice for healthcare and the helping professions. Since the CBI does not presuppose an American bias, (Kristensen, et al., 2005) usage of the CBI has allowed burnout research to expand on a global scale. In addition to being free, brief, global, psychometrically strong, and applicable to all professions (Dyrbye et al., 2018), a review of the literature found that no other researchers had heretofore used this instrument to measure librarian burnout. For these reasons, the authors selected the CBI for this study.

4. Findings

Table 1. Demographics Profile of Respondent (n=118)

	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender:	Female	85	72.0
	Male	33	28.0
Age:	18-20 years	10	8.5
	21-25 years	31	26.3
	26-30 years	49	41.5
	31-35 years	17	14.4
	36-40 years	7	5.9
	41-45 years	2	1.7
	46-50 years	2	1.7
Ethnicity:	Malay	106	89.8
	Indian	1	0.8
	Bumiputra	3	2.5
	Others	8	6.8
Education Level:	SPM/ O Level	11	9.3
	Diploma	8	6.8
	Bachelor Degree	86	72.9
	Master Degree	8	6.8
	PhD	5	4.2
	Like Joining Volunteerism:	Yes	104
No		3	2.5
Not sure		11	9.3
Years of volunteer activist:	None	15	12.7
	Less than 1	18	15.3
	1-2 years	13	11.0
	3-4 years	18	15.3
	5-6 years	6	5.1

	7-10 years	31	26.3
	11-15 years	13	11.0
	16-20 years	2	1.7
	21-25 years	2	1.7
Work Experience:			
	Less than 1	29	24.6
	1-2 years	22	18.6
	3-4 years	16	13.6
	5-6 years	24	20.3
	7-10 years	16	13.6
	11-15 years	6	5.1
	16-20 years	3	2.5
	21-25 years	1	0.8
	26 years over	1	0.8

Table 1 shows the result of the demographic profile. The respondents consisted of 72 per cent female and 28 percent male respondents. A total of 49 (41.5%) respondents were aged between 26 – 30 years old from the majority sample, followed by respondents who were in the range of 21 – 25 years old which is 31 (26.3%), 31 – 35 years old 17 (14.4%), 18 - 20 years old 10 (8.5%), 36 – 4- years old 7 (5.9%), 50 – 59 years old 2 (0.9%), 41 – 45 years old 2 (1.7%) and 46 – 50 years old also 2 (1.7%). The majority of respondents' ethnic groups where Malay is 106 (89.8%), others 8 (6.8%) which is international employees, bumiputra 3 (2.5%) and Indian 1 (0.8%). Almost all the respondents graduated with University Degree (72.9%), O-Level (9.3%), Diploma (6.8%), Master's (6.8%) and followed with Ph.D. (4.2%). Out of the 118 respondents, 88.1 percent of them liked joining the volunteerism program, while 9.3 percent were not sure and followed 2.5 percent did not like. A total of respondent involves as volunteer activist with 7-10 years (26.3%), 3-4 years (15.3%), less than 1 years (15.3%), no active as volunteer (12.7%), followed 1-2 years (11%), 11-15 years (11%), 5-6 years (5.1%), followed 16-17 years 1.7% and 21-25 years 1.7%. Mostly the respondent form operation department (35.6%), marketing (16.9%), Creative (15.3%), public relation (10.2%), finance (8.5%), human resource (5.9%), others (5,1%), and followed information technology (2.5%). Majority of respondent have less than 1 year work experience (24.6%), followed 5-6 years (20.3%), 1-2 years (18.6%), 3-4 years (13.6%), 7-10 years (13.6%), 11-15 years (5.1%), 16-20 years (2.5%), 21-25 years (0.8%) and followed 26 years over (0.8%).

The descriptive analysis consists of mean and standard deviation as shown in Table 2. The highest mean score is optimism dimension of PsyCap and it is found that efficacy dimension of Psycap scored the lowest mean among all variables. Overall, the variables scored a scale of 5 which was categorized as “moderate. The next step was to determine the normality of the data by analyzing the shape of the distribution. According to Coakes and Steed (2009), “.... the assumption of normality is a prerequisite for many inferential statistical techniques....” and Coakes and Ong (2011) stated that “normal distribution is acceptable when the skewness and kurtosis values are in the range of +/-3”. Moreover, Coakes and Ong (2011) indicated that the data with normal distribution will show that the plot will be distributed over a straight diagonal line. Based on Table 1, the data was determined as normally distributed, since the values of skewness and kurtosis were in the range of +/-3 for each variable. Hence the other analysis of inferential statistical techniques

can be explored. In this research, Cronbach Alpha is used to measure the reliability or internal consistency. Based on the result in Table 2, all Cronbach Alpha was between .67 to .94 which exceeded Nunally's (1978) minimum requirement of .60. The reliability value for all PsyCap's dimensions was between .77 to .88. Specifically, the reliability value for both emotional labour's dimensions were 0.67 and .93. Whereas, reliability value for burnout was .94.

Table 2. Results of Mean, Normality, and Reliability for All Variables (N=118)

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Reliability Cronbach's Alpha	Items
PsyCap - Hope	3.89	.68	-.377	-.205	.80	4
PsyCap - Efficacy	3.53	.83	-.856	1.829	.77	5
PsyCap - Resilience	3.61	.81	-.384	-.259	.81	5
PsyCap - Optimism	4.10	.76	-.556	-.453	.88	5
Emotional Labour – Surface Acting	3.76	.79	-.313	-.265	.67	3
Emotional Labour – Deep Acting	4.01	.91	-.718	-.371	.93	6
Burnout	3.89	.63	-.198	-.281	.94	16

Table 3. Pearson Correlation for All Variables (N=118)

	PsyCap - Hope	PsyCap - Efficacy	PsyCap - Resilience	PsyCap - Optimism	Emotional Labour – Surface Acting	Emotional Labour – Deep Acting	Burnout
PsyCap - Hope	1						
PsyCap - Efficacy	.525**	1					
PsyCap - Resilience	.465**	.528**	1				
PsyCap - Optimism	.471**	.535**	.611**	1			
Emotional Labour – Surface Acting	-.482**	-.428**	-.486**	-.490**	1		
Emotional Labour – Deep Acting	-.253**	-.369**	-.478**	-.340**	.342**	1	
Burnout	-.434**	-.530**	-.577**	-.437**	.518*	.590**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In this section, the Pearson correlation coefficients (r) were used to examine the relationship between PsyCap (hope, efficacy, resilience, optimism), emotional labour (surface acting, deep acting), and burnout. According to the Guilford Rule of Thumb, “the correlation coefficient r that is equal or more than 0.70 showed a strong relationship between variables if r coefficient is between the ranges of 0.30 to 0.69, the relationship is moderate and if r coefficient is less than 0.30, the relationship is considered weak”. Table 3 shows the result of the correlation between PsyCap dimensions and burnout with moderate correlation values, hope ($r=-.43$, $p<0.01$), efficacy ($r=-.53$, $p<0.01$), resilience ($r=-.58$, $p<0.01$), and optimism ($r=-.44$, $p<0.01$). These results indicate that there is a negative and significant correlation between PsyCap and burnout. On the other hand, the result of the

correlation between emotional labour's dimensions and burnout i.e., surface acting ($r=.52$, $p<0.01$), and deep acting ($r=.59$, $p<0.01$) with moderate correlation values respectively. The result indicates that there is a positive and significant correlation between emotional labour and burnout

Multiple Regression Analysis was used in this research to examine the effects between the independent and dependent variables (Sekaran, 2006). Table 4 below summarizes the result of a multiple regression analysis on the relationship between PsyCap (hope, efficacy, resilience, optimism), emotional labour (surface acting, deep acting), and burnout. The coefficient of determination (R^2 value) is the metric that is most often used to assess the structural model. This coefficient, which represents the square correlation between an endogenous construct's actual and anticipated values, serves as a gauge of the model's predictive precision. Better values indicate higher degrees of predicting accuracy, and the R^2 number ranges from 0 to 1 (Hair, 2013). The R^2 value between PsyCap, emotional labour, and burnout was .54. This research model explained that 54% of the variance in burnout is explained by PsyCap (hope, efficacy, resilience, optimism), and emotional labour (surface acting, deep acting). Table 3, shows the relationship between PsyCap (hope, efficacy, resilience, optimism), emotional labour (surface acting, deep acting), and burnout. Only two out of 4 dimensions of PsyCap were found to have a negative significant relationship with burnout i.e., efficacy and resilience. Therefore, only hypotheses H2, and H3 were supported, while hypotheses H1 and H4 were both not supported. Specifically, efficacy has a negative significant relationship with burnout ($\beta = -.19$, $p < .05$) with a t value of -2.27 , and resilience also had a negative significant relationship with burnout ($\beta = -.20$, $p < .05$) with a t value of -2.19 . Expectedly both dimensions of emotional labour were found to have positive significant effects on burnout, i.e., surface acting ($\beta = .20$, $p < .05$) with t value of 2.53 , and deep acting ($\beta = .35$, $p < .05$) with t value of 4.67 . Hence, hypotheses of H5, and H6 were both supported.

Table 4. Result of regression between Independent Variables and Dependent Variables

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.239	.348		3.556	.001
PsyCap - Hope	.066	.075	.072	.880	.381
PsyCap - Efficacy	-.145	.064	-.192	-2.266	.025
PsyCap - Resilience	-.166	.076	-.201	-2.189	.031
PsyCap - Optimism	.031	.068	.041	.460	.647
Emotional Labour – Surface Acting	.162	.064	.204	2.531	.013
Emotional Labour – Deep Acting	.240	.051	.349	4.673	.000

Note. Dependent Variable: Burnout, F- value: 21.926, Sig.: .000, R^2 : .542, Adjusted R^2 : .518

5. Discussion

NPO workers in Malaysia may find that psychological capital is particularly important, as they often work in high-stress environments and deal with challenging personal and social issues. Based on the results of this study, it was found that the resilience dimension of PsyCap was the most significant factor towards burnout, followed by the efficacy dimension and both effects were negative. Whereas both dimensions of hope and optimism were not significant. These findings indicated that an increase in either resilience or self-efficacy among the employees shall reduce their feelings of burnout. This study therefore had affirmed the previous studies by Arrogante and Aparicio-Zaldivar (2017), Rosenberg (2018) and Rushton et al. (2015) who had found the similar influence of PsyCap on employees' burnout. Thus, NPO workers can develop and maintain their psychological capital by engaging in various practices such as self-reflection, setting goals, and learning from failure (Zhou et al., 2020). They can also focus on building self-efficacy, which is the belief in one's ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish a task. Organizations can also support the development of psychological capital among their social workers by providing opportunities for professional development, fostering a positive work environment, and promoting work-life balance (Virga et al., 2020). It's worth noting that psychological capital is not a fixed trait, it can be developed and nurtured, and it may fluctuate based on life events and personal circumstances. The workers can benefit from regularly assessing and developing their psychological capital to ensure they have the resources they need to cope with the challenges of their work.

Additionally, both dimensions of emotional labour were found to have positive and significant impacts towards burnout. Between the two, deep action dimension was the strongest predictors, followed by surface acting. These findings therefore illustrated that an increment of either deep or surface acting shall increase the burnout among the NPO workers. Hence, this study contributed to the body of knowledge by conforming the same effect of emotional labour and burnout as recently studied by Zhang et al. (2018), Gerain and Zech (2019), Hori and Chao (2019) and Jeung et al. (2018). Thus, organizations can provide support by offering regular supervision, opportunities for continuing education, and providing adequate resources to help with the workload (WHO, 2019). To prevent burnout, NPO workers in Malaysia can implement self-care practices, such as setting boundaries, taking breaks, and seeking support from colleagues and supervisors (Menaldi et al., 2023). Excessive work hours, job discontent, and a lack of health and wellness practise such as regular exercise, medical care, and enough sleep have all been related to an elevated risk of burnout syndrome (Amofo et al., 2015; Iorga et al., 2017). Therefore, this study has contributed to the body of knowledge by adding evidence to enhance the literature about the impacts of psychological capital on efficacy and resilience, and emotional labour of surface and deep-acting towards employee burnout, especially among social workers.

6. Conclusion

This study adds to the growing body of literature on the idea of burnout, PsyCap and emotional labour in the workplace and is an important contribution. This study is special because it is being conducted in Malaysia rather than a Western setting. Instead of merely testing the association between workplace study aspects, this study also examines the

function of emotions in this relationship. The findings of this study would go into the most widely and intensive topics of burnout that have been studied and are currently still being researched by researchers of business, management, industrial and organisational psychology, and other disciplines. It is hoped that the findings would add to the existing body of knowledge and as a reference to other researchers and would act as a source of reference for government leaders and policymakers to come up with new policies, procedures, and guidelines. For this study, data were taken from the Malaysian context. As most of the studies were from western developed countries, this study's findings could increase the robustness of the theory of burnout among Malaysian public social care workers by establishing the existing theory of burnout within a different culture. It is an honest hope that this study's findings within Malaysia and ASEAN are an important finding for the nation and country that could be snowballed into something bigger in due time by other researchers worldwide.

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